
REHABILITATION OF PATIENTS WITH PROSOPAGNOSIA: A BRIEF CRITICAL EXAMINATION

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ABSTRACT

We can able to find a growing number of people suffering from a relatively rare pathological manifestation called face blindness or Prosopagnosia. Decades ago the disorder Prosopagnosia, was connected with religion and spirituality in most countries. Then, people, those who are suffering from face-blindness or Prosopagnosia were considered with the most discrimination and stigma. Because there was a superstition that this pathological manifestations or inability to recognize someone's face are due to god's curse or due to the influence of demon or satanic inhabitation on him. It was in the last some decades of the nineteenth century, it has been identified universally as a neurological and cognitive disorder or a clinical pathology. If we look at the clinical history of Prosopagnosia and its literature and other authentic data, we can understand that most of the works or clinical studies related to face-blindness or widely known as Prosopagnosia were about its biological areas such as its neural and psychological functions and dysfunctions. Only a very small amount of clinical researches has explained the importance of rehabilitation of people who are suffering from face blindness or Prosopagnosia. It is certainly very much important to know, comprehensive, more holistic, and much more elegant rehabilitation techniques to satisfy the victim's daily needs and activities. On the first level, we will cross-check very carefully that whether the neuroplasticity of the brain will change over the period of time to identify whether the timing of the treatment and onset of rehabilitation programs may be crucial to determine the outcome. And secondly in this paper, we will be analyzing various clinical/medical reports about the disorder Prosopagnosia, and finally, we will cross check its various types of rehabilitation methods and its upcoming or future paths. So the ultimate aim of this paper is to throw light on face blindness/processing or Prosopagnosia and understanding the neuroplasticity of the brain after a brain trauma and finally the rehabilitation of people with Prosopagnosia.

Keywords: Face Blindness, Prosopagnosia, Object/Face Recognition Abnormality, Neuroplasticity Of The Brain, Rehabilitation Techniques, And Cognitive Training.

I. INTRODUCTION

Prosopagnosia or popularly known as face blindness is often considered as a neurological and cognitive distortion. We can say that it is selective disorientation to recognize or identify faces or any other objects. It was recently identified that a very small amount of people after a severe or mild traumatic brain injury or any other form of neurodegenerative disorder, especially on the brain area called occipitotemporal regions will manifest a small degree of face recognition difficulties [1], [2]. In a research study, it was already found that, around 2.9% of the population exhibit the symptoms-developmental Prosopagnosia (DP).

Developmental Prosopagnosia or DP is considered as a type of clinical pathology, occurs in general people without any clear trace of traumatic brain injury or any other types of neurodegenerative disorders on their brain [3]. In some cases, people surmount very well from Prosopagnosia whereas others are relatively less to satisfy their daily needs and activities and their occupational demands as well [4], [5]. Meanwhile, it is very difficult to say that most of the studies related to Prosopagnosia whether it is acquired or developmental Prosopagnosia, the concentrations of all those studies were its neurological functioning rather than its remediation. It is also important to mention that not all Prosopagnosia cases need rehabilitation or any other

interventional approach if the person with Prosopagnosia has identified its alternative to identify faces or objects or he or she has developed his or her strategies to cope up with this disorder [6]. However, a study conducted by Yardley et al. it is identified that the majority of the subjects manifested negative psychological and social experiences related to Prosopagnosia, especially, relatively at a younger age level. In this paper, we examine the rehabilitation strategies of people with Prosopagnosia whether it is acquired Prosopagnosia (AP) or developmental Prosopagnosia (DP) by analyzing clinical observations and data.

The aim of neuropsychological rehabilitation is by providing training to the victims how to satisfy his or her personal daily needs with great satisfaction or how to adopt proper coping strategies to overcome Prosopagnosia [7]. So, in the circumstance of the rehabilitation dimension, the apex objective is to strengthen or prepare the patient to develop alternative or compensatory overall rehabilitation strategies that helps the patient to recognize faces and objects. The area of rehabilitation is very wide, meanwhile, it is important to understand that only a small amount of effort has been put to study about Prosopagnosia related rehabilitation strategies.

II. RELATED WORKS

Many clinical and non-clinical research studies have been done in relation with Prosopagnosia and Neuroplasticity. The general conscience of the treatment of Prosopagnosia is relies only on symptomatic management rather than to treat the root cause of the disorder. To date there is no any clear treatment protocol or medication discovered to manage people with Prosopagnosia. Table 1 contains some of the clinical and non clinical trials conducted universally to identify accurate rehabilitation strategies to manage patients.

Table 1: Review of Prosopagnosia Rehabilitation and Face Processing trials

S. No	Title	Focus	Reference
1	The neuropsychology of face processing during infancy and childhood	Face recognition problems of childhood and infancy and its remedial interventions.	De Haan M. (2001). [8]
2	Developmental Prosopagnosia: a case analysis and treatment study.	Study of Prosopagnosia in children with intense perceptual and receiving difficulties.	Brunsdon R. (2006). [9]
3	Training of familiar face recognition and visual scan paths for faces in a child with congenital Prosopagnosia.	Training of pediatric patients with Prosopagnosia.	Schmalzl L. (2008). [10]
4	Functional plasticity in ventral temporal cortex following cognitive rehabilitation of a congenital prosopagnosic.	Difference in plasticity and depending upon this deference; arrangement or planning of treatment.	DeGutis J. M (2007). [11]
5	Holistic face training enhances face processing in developmental Prosopagnosia.	Comprehensive approaches which can be done within three months to decrease the effects of Prosopagnosia.	DeGutis J. (2014). [12]
6	The Cambridge face memory test: results for neurologically intact individuals and an investigation of its validity using inverted face stimuli and prosopagnosic subjects.	To analyze the degree of Prosopagnosia and to decide what are the treatment/rehabilitation strategies should be taken to manage the disorder.	Duchaine B. C. (2006). [13]
7	Training in face-processing skills for a child with acquired Prosopagnosia.	Various cognitive training strategies to reduce the effects of Prosopagnosia.	Ellis H. D. (1988). [14]

III. OBJECTIVES

The main objectives of this paper are given below:

- (1). To identify the process of neuroplasticity.
- (2). To identify the relationship between neuroplasticity and Prosopagnosia.
- (3). Throw light on rehabilitation process.
- (4). To analyze the interventional models.
- (5). Future directions of the rehabilitation methods.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This paper consists of identifying various rehabilitation methods used universally to manage people with Prosopagnosia. The main sources of information in this paper collected through secondary data such as authentic journals, articles and official websites.

V. NEUROPLASTICITY AND FACE-RECOGNITION:AN OVERVIEW

Typically the word "neuroplasticity" means that a neural structure's ability to learn or adapt novel skills or improve its existing efficiencies after brain trauma or any other neurological damage or during the normal course of development [15]. If we grasp the clinical literature, we can easily able to find the two most important or apex theories about the brain's neuroplasticity [16]. The first and foremost theory pointing that, there is an inbuilt cognitive system for a special action or function and this inbuilt system develops during human development. Again, on the next level, this theory clutches the notion that, once the special or particular neural systems have been assigned for their work, no kind of damage can able to cause permanent and long-term dysfunction. The human body gradually will start to adopt a complementary strategy to function again to overcome the lost or damaged biological and psychic functions. In the context of the human face processing, after the neural degeneration or damage of our highly specialized brain region, the human body will gradually acquire a clear and natural complementary strategy to overcome the lost function by adapting some skills like identifying face by analyzing individual face patterns or by adapting special semantic cues during a face-recognizing process, etc. On the other hand, another theoretical perspective upholds the view that the human brain has a natural and special ability to retain its plasticity throughout our life and some hidden or dormant reserves may help us to acquire new or compensatory skills to substitute the damaged or destroyed brain areas. Famous scientist Thomas explains that the natural function and structure of the human brain are not built to irreversibly resolute by an innate or inbuilt plan, but the base concept of the brain's plasticity is also greatly finite [17]. Further, it is very important to understand that, these limitations are more possible to undulate during our development.

VI. PERCEPTUAL NARROWING

An important and popular theory about the development of human face-processing stress that as we all are exposed to facial recognition. As a result of our visual experience with faces will develop at our early stages itself. This theory is globally known as the "perceptual narrowing" hypothesis [18]. Some of its clinical evidence supporting this perceptual narrowing theory is from the experimental results very in young infants and they can recognize between other-race faces. But on the other hand older infants and adult children lack this kind of ability [19]. Meanwhile, all the clinical research findings throwing light on the information that in the first few months of life infants have the plasticity in the human face- processing, researcher Nelson also put forth the principle that this type of brain's ability to recognize the face at the early stages of life is because of the specialization of neural connections and neural tissues for face-processing and in later years of life it may also lead to an absence of plasticity.

Studies about behavioral processes observing the exposure of face-recognizing ability also propose that a comprehensive and specialized face-recognizing skill emerges from the early stages of our course of development itself. Through a comprehensive and structural review of the developmental study conducted until now states that there is a window for plasticity which remains only within the first years of development [20], [21]. With the concrete agreement of all the aforementioned scientific studies, authors came to the general conclusion that children especially as young as five years of age, no doubts, they have developed or manifested

an adult-like super ability to recognize perpetrators from a target-present line-ups. In total, generally, we can easily understand that there is no much noticeable qualitative change in recognition of faces beyond a maximum of four to five years of human development. In another level, it has also been pointed out that even infant babies are very much capable of a holistic face processing [22]; it is also possible that the infant is capable to develop the face-processing ability at a very early stage of his or her development itself but exerting a limit on the brain plasticity beyond the stage of early periods of childhood. This particular notion is very much openly supported by some other research studies. In those clinical studies, researchers have precisely observed some adult and adolescent experimental subjects who have started their life with a severe ophthalmic disorder called a cataract. The most astonishing fact that those cataracts were surgically removed before the period of seven months itself, but, unfortunately, all those children manifested a very much noticeable disoriented or distorted face-processing ability [23], [24] [25] but children's very ability to process or discriminate normal object stress the point that to develop a great face-processing skill we need to have a visual input mechanism at the early stage of life itself [26], [27]. Conclusively, we can say that it is raising the importance of early visual input to form a normal and healthy face-processing ability.

There is another important point that studies have identified the connection between early visual input ability to face processing skills. But it is very important to notice that these face-recognizing abilities are possible to be refined later years of human life. Through a clinical neuroimaging study, it is identified that the human cortical face-processing mechanism is subjected to development until the adolescence period [28]. A scientific clinical study conducted by Gathers and his coworkers suggested the point that the stimulation or activeness of fusiform gyrus is not considered as much great as to recognize faces in comparison with objects until around 10 years of age, and yet, they have vividly mentioned an important notion, especially in relation with an above study that that kind of activation in the brain more posteriorly in the part of inferior occipital region [29], [30]. There are also so many core researches about the neuroplasticity of adulthood. All these studies support the fact that our brain has a great ability to retain its plasticity even in the adulthood period as well. The result of these studies paving the basement of the notion about the brain's ability to retain its ability or capability to retain its plasticity even at the advanced period of human life as well. Related to this notion, Germine et al. researched with over 60,000 people age limit starting from pre-adolescence to till middle-age on their capacity to recognize and learn new faces [31]. In other clinical research, Germine and his companions found another finding that the ability to recognize faces improves until 30 years of period. Meanwhile, the ability to recognize inverted faces and names develops relatively at a much prior age.

VII. OTHER- RACE EFFECT

Another study put a notion forward that we are far better to recognize faces from our clan or races than from a different race and this is widely known as the other-race effect [32]. This study also supports the brain's ability to retain its plasticity. A study on the other-race effect explains that people are more familiar with the faces of their races and they are lacking the experience of mingling with people of another race. This makes them a little difficult to recognize faces from another race [33]. This phenomenon has already been observed among infants, especially at the age of around 3 months [34], [35]; and some studies propose that the brain remains plastic and even it can be reversed naturally in adulthood. A study conducted by Hancock and Rhodes mentioned a much-reduced level of other-race effect. The reason for this reduced other-race effect was, the participants were very much familiar with people from other races [36], [37], [38]. In short, studies from multiple dimension such as behavioral, neural, neuroimaging investigations, etc. with typical participants proposes the notion that our brain retains its plasticity naturally to some extent and thus the ability of face processing or face recognition also plastic in nature. In the older age there, the plasticity seems to be relatively slow but there is plasticity. This finding shows the ray of hope that there is a possibility to rehabilitate people with difficulty face recognition skills.

VIII. TIMING OF TRAUMA

There are some studies about the time of impact and intervention. There is a universal perspective that the human brain has a greater ability to retain its plasticity in the developing period than the adult brain [39]; and Hutten ocher suggests that, among the whole available Neuro rehabilitation literature, it has been mentioned

that neuroplasticity is noticeably lower than children. In some clinical studies, it has been observed that there is a presence of some special proteins and genes which are very much helpful to regenerate neuronal growth and synaptogenesis. The presence of these proteins becomes less compare to the childhood period [40]. So that the supplementary restructuring and natural transfer of its functions are very much likely to happen after an early age brain trauma or any other type of degeneration in the brain [41]. So that we can conclude that a fast recovery from face-processing disorder occurs in children than in adult people. Some studies suggest that even without any rehabilitation interventions there is a great possibility to overcome from face-processing deficit [42], but this is not consistent all the time. There are some studies, found no noticeable improvement of face-processing ability over time [43], [44]. In some clinical studies, it has been observed that early level trauma is more amenable to rehabilitation programs.

IX. AGE OF INJURY AND ITS NEUROREHABILITATION SUCCESS

The age of brain trauma or degeneration is an important factor in the success of neuro rehabilitation techniques. For example, from the clinical data about stroke, it is evident that early intervention of stroke is more likely to subside through early intervention. Because there are parallel connections between the plasticity of the human brain and the naturally developing human nervous system and this helps to reverse adult human brains to retain its plasticity and functions immediately after the stroke. The need for immediate intervention is the key factor to determine the later growth of plasticity. If there is no early intervention happens, the plasticity of the brain gets weakened immediately after the trauma [45] [46] [47]. This example suggests the point that the human brain is more sensitive or receptive to early interventions.

X. LOCATION AND SIZE OF BRAIN LESIONS

There are lots of reasons that cause to bring Prosopagnosia, such as stroke, a clinical procedure called temporal lobectomy, neoplasm, etc. New studies also reported a degenerative disorder called front temporal lobar degeneration also causes Prosopagnosia. With these verities of causes, attempt to give rehabilitation to Prosopagnosia patient, must understand the area of the lesion and its neurological damage and especially how different types of brain damages brings different types of deficits. It has already been mentioned that neuro rehabilitation is mostly person-centered. Rehabilitation techniques must be adjusted or designed with the victim's special needs. In a study, it has been identified that in most clinical cases, primarily the trauma affected on the posterior regions of the brain. If the area of trauma is larger means, more difficult to overcome the disorder even though rehabilitation helps to slow down the prognosis.

XI. COMPREHENSIVE IMPLICATIONS FOR REHABILITATION

There are many debates about what kind of rehabilitation technique is more helpful to overcome the disorder. Some suggest remedial rehabilitation training is more useful to treat patients with Prosopagnosia while some other states' behavioral compensatory mechanisms will help more to overcome the disorder. There is no universal consensus about which type of rehabilitation technique is more helpful to manage or treat Prosopagnosia. Most of the clinicians are more comfortable and satisfied to use individually tailored or individually designed rehabilitation techniques. There are no many clinical studies about rehabilitation techniques of patients with Prosopagnosia. Based on the limited clinical data and literature, it is observed that compensatory rehabilitation techniques are more useful than remedial rehabilitation techniques. But, for patients with unilateral brain lesions, remedial rehabilitation training seems to be very much useful.

XII. SPECIFICITY OF INTERVENTIONAL MODULES

It is evident from the above mentioned clinical studies that, the most useful rehabilitation program is those that mainly concentrate the deficit itself. Especially, the clinical studies reported that training or rehabilitation in a comprehensive manner – is a dynamic mechanism that helps to relive difficulties from Prosopagnosia. In this study, researchers attempted to teach some neurotypical people in a comprehensive process using an inverted face. But the result was negative. The reason is not clear why training with inverted faces is not responding to holistic training? The assumption is that it may be due to the fact, there is a limitation to the transfer of perceptual learning skill and upright faces are different from inverted faces. So, the victims were not able to generalize it.

XIII. FUTURE DIRECTIONS OF NEUROREHABILITATION

The base strategy to rehabilitate people with Prosopagnosia is individually designed holistic training ranging from remedial training to compensatory strategies. Meanwhile, more research is needed to identify its suitability in every victim. Till now there is no specific rehabilitation training or techniques which are being used universally as same. Neurorehabilitation of people with Prosopagnosia is now considered as asymptomatic rehabilitation by designing special aids to recognize faces and objects for a single person's needs. Although, so much research is being conducted in this regard. Future rehabilitation researches should concentrate on the victim's emotional responses as well. Another area is everyday face recognition training. The concept of everyday face recognition is now under great consideration. There are some clinical interventions, which seems to be effective in Prosopagnosia patients. Especially, two types of clinical methodologies are considered as very much effective to treat Prosopagnosia and they are intranasal inhalation of a substance called oxytocin and the other is non-invasive brain stimulation. Now, current clinical findings suggest that the intranasal inhalation of oxytocin will only work temporarily. There is no clinical finding of its long-term action on Prosopagnosia. Oxytocin is a substance that comes under the category of neuropeptide and it is generally considered to elevate social cognition.

The second technique is non-invasive brain stimulation. If we look at the clinical literature we can understand the wide verity of non-invasive brain stimulation. There are only three types of stimulation techniques, which are relatively useful in the context of Prosopagnosia. The first type of stimulation is called transcranial electric stimulation (it is the method of conjoining two types of non-invasive stimulation techniques- transcranial direct current stimulation or shortly DCS, and transcranial random noise stimulation or shortly RNS) and the last one is galvanic vestibular stimulation (GVS). Studies are being questioned about the effectiveness of these techniques in Prosopagnosia victims. But yet, some findings show it is effective for at least a short span of period. More studies and researches need to be conducted to find its actual effectiveness on Prosopagnosia.

XIV. STUDY FINDINGS

Prosopagnosia is a disorder and relatively very less known to society. Studies on Prosopagnosia found that the human brain retains its plasticity throughout life. But what makes things worst is, the human brain keeps the greater amount of plasticity till adulthood and as we get aged the brain will lack its ability to retain its plasticity. Once the brain lacks its plasticity, it is difficult to overcome the disorder beyond a level. Neuro rehabilitation of patients with Prosopagnosia seems to be very much effective if the intervention starts immediately after the brain injury or any other neurodegenerative disorder. But there too some components are determinants of its effectiveness on Prosopagnosia such as victim's age, the gravity of injury or neuronal degeneration, overall health status, etc. rehabilitation consists of or based on two main concepts, they are compensatory and remedial rehabilitation plans. In some cases, remedial intervention programs are shown to be more effective while in other cases compensatory interventions found more useful. The main reason for this phenomenon is individual differences. So, while planning rehabilitation modalities one should keep this fact in mind, every person is different and thus their needs and demands are also different. So, rehabilitation techniques should be individually tailored at least to some extent so that the victim might feel more comfortable and satisfied with their new circumstances.

XV. CONCLUSION

In sum, in this study, we have gained information about the plasticity of the brain, face-blindness, and rehabilitation techniques. In this study, all the journals and notions published were taken from authentic sources and so the value of information hereby ascertained. In the context of rehabilitation of people with Prosopagnosia, it is the therapist's discretion to use an effective rehabilitation program, but it should provide satisfaction and improvement to the person. Overall, support from family and colleagues are very much needed to overcome the situation. Apart from any treatment plan or any rehabilitation technique. In sum, in this study, we have gained information about the plasticity of the brain, face-blindness, and rehabilitation techniques. In this study, all the journals and notions published were taken from authentic sources and so the value of information hereby ascertained. In the context of rehabilitation of people with Prosopagnosia, it is the therapist's discretion to use an effective rehabilitation program, but it should provide satisfaction and

improvement to the person. Overall, support from family and colleagues are very much needed to overcome the situation. Apart from any treatment plan or any rehabilitation technique, the confidence of the patients is the main revitalizing energy to surmount the situation. So, the great participation of the therapist and the patient's family is a key determinant to the improvement of the disorder.

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